

RESIST

Fostering Queer Feminist Intersectional Resistances against Transnational Anti-Gender Politics

The RESIST Project: Press Release

FINDINGS FROM THE 2nd STAGE OF THE PROJECT RELEASED

Headline: RESIST reveals the depth of impact of the so called ‘anti-gender’ politics on lives of cis-women, trans people, LGBTIQ+ groups.

Lead: *RESIST project has shown multiple, negative consequences of the so-called ‘anti gender’ politics across Europe. RESIST has also captured creative and common ways how women and minoritised communities cope with, and resist, the oppressive and anti democratic mobilisations, which undermine basic civil liberties.*

The RESIST project (<https://theresistproject.eu>) has released results from its 2nd stage of research, demonstrating widespread consequences of the so-called ‘anti-gender’ politics across Europe.

Main text: The report demonstrates that, in all case studies, including those from societies perceived as "progressive", feminists and LGBTIQ+ individuals face verbal and physical attacks, property damage, and systemic discrimination, often in public spaces and on social media. These acts of violence contribute to their marginalisation. Their recognition is hindered by legal and administrative obstacles, exacerbated by a lack of institutional support. "Anti-gender" discourses and mobilisations are becoming increasingly institutionalised, bolstered by polarising media and political narratives.

Anti-gender mobilisations have significant effects on the targeted individuals or groups. These include detrimental impacts on both mental and physical health. Many individuals expressed feelings of vulnerability, as well as the consequences on their daily lives, such as fear, exhaustion, and anxiety. These effects are particularly severe for those with intersecting marginalised identities, who face additional forms of discrimination, even within the LGBTIQ+ and feminist collectives that are supposed to support them. Despite these challenges, targeted individuals resist by mobilising collectively, creating safer spaces, and raising public awareness.

Quote: “Despite the pervasive nature of ‘anti-gender’ attacks, feminists and LGBTIQ+ individuals do not see themselves as mere passive victims. They are actively

engaged in efforts to challenge these discourses and policies, while striving to create safer and more liveable spaces for themselves.” – Extract from the Resist report.
The RESIST project is co-ordinated by University College Dublin in collaboration with Edinburgh Napier University, European University Viadrina, Université Paris 1 Panthéon Sorbonne, Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts, Université de Lausanne, Université de Fribourg, Universitat Pompeu Fabra, and Feminist Autonomous Centre for research, Maynooth University.

RESIST is a four-year study supported by the research councils and funding bodies of the European Union, UK and Switzerland. More information about the project on its website: <https://theresistproject.eu>

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union under Project ID 101060749.
EU Horizon Europe (EU partners); UK Government Horizon Europe Guarantee Scheme (UK partner);
Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (Swiss partners).

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or British and Swiss funding authorities. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.